

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BANABOTLHE****FIRST NAME: MOGOMOTSI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your five key concepts with a page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Basics of essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Examples of plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Effective use of punctuations (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. Chicago Style of Writing (EUCLID 2019, 24)
5. Diversity of English Language (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have had challenges with academic writing both as an undergraduate and graduate student. Yaley (2017) confirms that students who have English as their second language have similar challenges as the one I faced with academic writing. Most non-native English speakers are not conversant with English academic papers' conventions (Defazio et al. 2010). As a non-native English speaker, I found the information in the course pack very enlightening and exciting. So far, I am ready to apply the concept and conventions learned to write my first response paper.

The response paper discusses the insights I got from reading notes for period one. It evaluates insights from five areas of the coursepack: plagiarism, variants of English language, style guide, punctuations, and essay writing.

2) THE ART OF ESSAY WRITING

I found material for period one insightful and informative. The language used to present the notes is easy to comprehend and digest. Like Yaley (2017), the period considers

writing academic papers as the hallmark of graduate studies. It has inspired me to invest time to learn and perfect my art of academic writing through practice.

a) Essay writing

The message from the section on essay writing is that we must take time to plan our response. It has guided me on the steps to take to prepare an answer to an essay. Following these steps makes academic writing a process with a straightforward procedure for achieving an end. Hence, I accept the advice given by EUCLID (2019, 1) that I should devote time to research, read, and analyze the question. Dedicating time to plan helps me crystalize the action, format, and information required to answer the question.

Indeed, essay writing should define the thesis statement, which is the foundation for developing the essay (EUCLID 2019,1). I discovered that the thesis statement derives from the essay question through a process of critical analysis. Critical analysis helps to decipher the action required to answer the question. Without a known thesis statement, the activities entailed in answering the question become haphazard. So, the thesis statement gives structure to activities undertaken to respond to the question asked. In short, it guides the process of research, structuring information, picking examples and evidence (EUCLID 2019, 3).

The best advice I got from the coursepack was to write the essay as early as possible (EUCLID 2019, 1). Starting early accords one enough time to plan, write, edit and rewrite the paper.

b) Examples of plagiarism

I unequivocally agree with EUCLID (2019, 5) that plagiarism is unethical and morally wrong. Those who commit it compromise the integrity of the research and education system and therefore deserve punishment. The evil represented by plagiarism is theft and deceit. In my view, using another person's words as your own is tantamount to stealing them, which deserves punishment. It is deceitful when one fails to reference their previous work. In both cases, the offenders are looking for recognition through evil ways.

I noticed how plagiarism happens during academic writing. At first, it was hard to accept paraphrasing as plagiarism, but the notes caused me to change my mind. Certainly, paraphrasing qualifies as plagiarism because it involves restructuring other people's ideas to fit a context. Paraphrasing retains the original opinion expressed by the sentence. Hence, the paraphrased material should be referenced in-text and under the list of work (EUCLID 2019, 6).

The scales of academic justices are correct to classify substituting a few words in a sentence as plagiarism. Just like paraphrasing, replacing a few words on a sentence does not change the original views it expresses. The act modifies the flow of the idea to fit into a new circumstance.

Equally wrong and worthy of punishment is failing to reference one's views from previous work. Such an act allows one to receive recognition for the same material multiple times. I support the punishment of those who commit self-plagiarism as well.

I consider contract cheating the worst form of plagiarism among them all. No reason is good enough to justify why people engage in it. As a result, I strongly support advocacy to reprimand those who practice it harshly. No one, whoever they are, should be allowed to tarnish the integrity of the research and education system through contract cheating. I abhor contract cheating because it causes people to receive recognition for the work produced for them by others.

Plagiarism has no place in the academic world as it diminishes the integrity of the research and education system.

c) The variants of the English language

My country, Botswana, a former British Protectorate, uses English as an official language. Consequently, our education system adopted Standard British English (SBE) as a de facto official English variant for communication. I am more proficient in communicating in SBE than in any other variant.

Euclid recommends Standard American English (SAE) as the preferred variant for writing assignments (EUCLID 2019, 28). Since EUCLID (2019, 28) confirms that SBE and SAE are different, I foresee myself struggling to write assignments using the SAE as advised by the university. I will rely on grammar software and the course pack to assist with editorial and other writing conventions as mitigation.

I did not know the difference between the two variants until after reading the course notes. It is then that I realized that I have been confusing the two variants in my write-ups, especially when it comes to words the two variants spell or pronounce the same by the variants. I foresee the confusion extending to words “that have the same spelling but different pronunciation, same pronunciation but different spelling, same words with different or additional meanings and same term with different but similar pronunciation and spelling, (EUCLID 2019, 29).” Similarly, I anticipate struggling to write dates, numbers, and honorifics using the SAE. It will take a while before I adapt and become comfortable with using the SAE format.

There are areas where I am already adjusting to using the SAE. Reading American novels gave me comfort to express collective nouns and pluralized adjectives using the SAE.

d) The style guide

The section gave me insights into why academic disciplines differ in how they present academic writing. EUCLID (2019, 24) attributes differences in the writing styles between academic disciplines using a style guide. Each domain uses the style guide to

define the standard element of a writing style (EUCLID 2019, 24). The details of a writing style account for the differences in contents presentation seen between academic fields.

I find the style guide as a convenient writing tool that works for individuals and teams. The style guide lends itself as a valuable tool for doing editorial, collaborating, and structuring write-ups for both groups. It offers groups the means to standardize and harmonize their style to the writing policy of the client.

I consider the style guide an indispensable writing tool for individuals and teams alike. It helps writers to produce work that meets their objective, customer expectations and aligns with prevailing writing policies.

e) Effective use of Punctuations

I found the material presented in the course too abstract to understand without referring to another source for clarity. The section throws in technical terms and phrases without defining them or giving them context through examples. For instance, we see words and phrases such as conjunctions, dependent clauses, and sentence modifiers thrown at us without being explained or given context. I find how these terms and phrases are introduced to the reader intimidating to a non-native English speaker.

I do not think the section has achieved its purpose of teaching us how to use a comma in our writing. It needs to be revised to include definitions, descriptions of technical phrases, and examples to achieve that end. I believe defining and describing technical words will enhance the reader's understanding. Adding these changes will transform the section into a quick read that also serves as reference material on using a comma for those using English as a second language.

I find the presentation on apostrophes more relevant and adequate, unlike with a comma. The use of examples illuminates how apostrophes express possession in singular nouns and plural nouns.

3) CONCLUSION

The coursepack provides a good foundation for inducting us on academic writing. It lends itself as reference material that can guide academic writing from time to time. As a graduate student, the period has offered me the foundational skill to write an essay following the English language writing conventions

REFERENCES

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